

METHODS OF DYNAMIC STRENGTH CALCULATION OF LEVER-DISK FRICTION SHOCK ABSORBERS OF ER9E ELECTRIC TRAIN

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<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejar-v03-i02-p2-66>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 02nd February 2023

Accepted: 12th February 2023

Online: 13th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Electric train, friction shock absorber, the rational dimensions of parts of friction shock absorber, improved calculating methods.

ABSTRACT

The article presents new methods for dynamic strength calculation of the lever-disk friction shock absorbers of the ER9E electric train.

The main type of friction that occurs between the disks of a lever-disk friction shock absorber of electric trains is frictional friction [1, 2, 3]. There, molecular adhesion leads to the formation of bonds between the films that cover the rubbing pairs. Under the shear, they are destroyed. Due to the roughness and waviness of the friction surfaces, the contact of the pairs occurs on sites. On sites with low pressure, elastic strain takes place, and on sites with high pressure, plastic strain takes place. The actual area of contact between the pairs is represented by the sum of the small sites. The dimensions of the contact sites are 30-50 microns; under an increase in load, they grow and unite.

During the destruction, heat is generated on the sites, and chemical processes take place. There are three groups of wear: mechanical - in the form of abrasive wear, molecular-chemical - in the form of plastic strain or brittle fracture, and corrosion-mechanical - in the form of corrosive or oxidative wear [2, p. 87-88].

The active wear factor is the gaseous environment that generates oxidative wear. The formation of an oxide film protects friction pairs from direct contact and setting. Therefore, oxidative wear is the only permissible one.

The strength of the molecular bonds of the contacted layer should be less than that of the deep layers. The plasticity of the surface layer contributes to the reduction of specific pressures and improves the run-in ability of the material. These provisions led to the development of composite materials.

An important factor is the temperature regime of the friction pair. Heat causes physical-chemical processes in the friction layer, converting binders into liquid fractions that act as a lubricant. Iron-based cermet materials contribute to an increase in the coefficient of friction and wear resistance.

The fast run-in ability of rubbing pairs is important. It leads to rapid local wear and an increase in the contour contact area of the bodies. At slow run-in ability, local temperatures lead to undesirable local changes in the friction material.

Friction is the resistance that occurs between rubbing pairs as a result of molecular-mechanical adhesion of roughness. Under relative shift of the pairs, the bonds are destroyed, heat is generated on the contact sites, chemical-oxidative processes and destruction occur in the form of plastic strain, abrasive and corrosion-oxidative wear. Excessive pressure exceeding the setting threshold leads to the destruction of the oxide film, and local tear of the material, followed by abrasive destruction of the friction surface. The ingress of dust, sand and other foreign particles from the surrounding medium leads to the abrasive destruction of not only the contact layer but also of deeper layers.

Rapid run-in of rubbing pairs accelerates local wear and increases the area of their contact with a decrease in pressure and stabilization of friction. Composite friction materials give elasticity to the friction layers, reducing the pressure and improving the run-in of the material. Iron-based cermet materials contribute to an increase in the coefficient of friction and wear resistance.

The loading of a friction pair is understood as a set of operating conditions: the pressure of the friction surfaces (2-10 MPa), the relative slippage speed of the pairs (0.1-0.2 m/s), the duration of one loading cycle (0.2-0.4 s), hourly average number of loadings (200-1500 cycles), contact layer temperature ($\leq 200^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The main requirements for the friction pair of friction shock absorbers of railways rolling stock are stability of the friction coefficient, high wear resistance of the pair, low modulus of elasticity and material hardness, low coefficient of thermal expansion, good run-in of the friction material, sufficient mechanical strength, anti-corrosion, unsetting, heat resistance and other friction properties [1, 2, 3].

The main factors of friction instability of the friction shock absorber are the violation of the technology of manufacturing friction elements (non-compliance with the temperature regime during vulcanization, heat treatment, etc.); deviations in the dimensions of individual parts, even within the established tolerances; design imperfection with high sensitivity to changes in the friction coefficient.

In this regard, it is relevant to develop new methods for calculating the dynamic strength of the lever-disk friction shock absorber of the ER9E electric train.

The indicators of stability of friction shock absorbers include the rate of change of the friction force P with a change in the friction coefficient μ ; absorber sensitivity to technological errors, i.e. to deviations from geometrical parameters.

Patterns of the normal process of abrasive wear of friction dampers are: the amount of wear Δ is proportional to the path s of friction $\Delta = K_S s$ and the intensity of wear $\delta = \dot{\Delta} \approx K_S v$ is proportional to the friction velocity $= s$; the amount of wear does not depend on the friction velocity and is determined by the specific load p , the coefficient of sliding friction μ , and the operating time t of the friction shock absorber

$$k_p = K_S(p, \mu, t); \quad (1)$$

the wear rate per unit friction path $\frac{d\Delta}{ds} = k_p p$ is proportional to the specific load p , $\delta = \Delta \approx K_p p v$; the measure of wear rate $p v$ should not exceed the norms developed by practice, $p v \leq C$, $p < 2$ MPa, the wear value is inversely related to the hardness H of material.

The methods for calculating the dynamic strength of lever-disk friction shock absorbers consist of the following stages:

1. Calculation of the required pre-load force of disks N .

According to the required friction moment $M_T = P\ell$ between k surfaces of the friction disks with given inner D_{in} and outer D_{ou} diameters, the required disk pre-load force is calculated as

$$M_T = P\ell = \frac{kN\mu(D_{in}^3 - D_{ou}^3)}{3(D_{in}^2 - D_{ou}^2)}, \quad (2)$$

$$N = \frac{3P\ell}{\mu k D_{ou}} \cdot \frac{1 - \delta^2}{1 - \delta^3}; \quad \delta = \frac{D_{in}}{D_{ou}} \approx 0,6 \div 0,7. \quad (3)$$

2. Calculation of the required friction moment M_{fr} .

$M_{fr} = P\ell$ between k surfaces of friction disks

$$M_T = \frac{kN\mu(D_{in}^3 - D_{ou}^3)}{3(D_{in}^2 - D_{ou}^2)}. \quad (4)$$

3. Calculation of the required pre-load force of disks N .

$$N = \frac{3P\ell}{\mu k D_{ou}} \cdot \frac{1 - \delta^2}{1 - \delta^3}. \quad (5)$$

4. Injection of allowable pressure between friction pairs, for example for asbestos plates,

$$p = \frac{N}{F} \leq p_{max} = 1,5 \cdot 10^6 \text{ N/m}^2 = 1,5 \text{ MPa} \quad (6)$$

and the determination of pre-load limits and disks diameters

$$N < \frac{\pi D_H^2}{4} (1 - \delta^2) p_{max}; \quad (7)$$

$$D_{ou}^2 > \frac{12P\ell}{\pi p_{max} \mu k} \cdot \frac{1}{1 - \delta^2}; \quad D_{in} = \delta D_{ou}. \quad (8)$$

For a known compression force N , the spring pressure is calculated. The coil diameter D and the spring index $i = \frac{D}{d} = 4 \div 8$ are taken, and the coefficients of spring stiffness increase k_1 and decrease k_2 are calculated: $k_1 = 1 + 1,25i^{-1} + 0,875i^{-2}$; $k_2 = 1 + 0,5i^{-1} - 0,5i^{-2}$.

For the allowable torsional stress, the diameter of the bar is calculated

$$d^2 > \frac{8iNk_1}{\pi \tau_{max}}, \quad \tau_{max} = 650 \text{ N/mm}^2; \quad (9)$$

5. Calculation of spring stiffness C , spring deformations f and f_{max} , free height h_{fh} , and loaded spring step h in mm.

Then, the stiffness of the spring is calculated for the accepted number of working coils n

$$C = \frac{Gd^4}{8nD^2k_2}; \quad G = 80\,000 \text{ N/mm}^2. \quad (10)$$

Using known deformations f and f_{max} , the free height h_{fh} and the step of the loaded spring h in mm are determined as

$$f = \frac{N}{C}, \quad f_{max} = \frac{N_{max}}{C}; \quad (11)$$

$$h_{fh} = (n + 1)(d + 1) + f_{max}; \quad h = (n + 1 + f_{max})n^{-1} + d. \quad (12)$$

6. Calculation of rubber-metal elements.

Rubber-metal elements are installed, as a rule, at the ends of the lever linkage of absorbers. Structurally, the outer D and inner d diameters of the element are set and the allowable compressive stress $\sigma_{max} = 1,5 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and the allowable relative deformation $\varepsilon_{max} = 0,2$ are set.

With two linkages, the pre-compression force of the elements is:

$$P_0 = \frac{kp}{2}, \quad k = 1,2, \quad (13)$$

the area and compressive stress are specified

$$F_{comp} = \frac{\pi}{4}(D^2 - d^2); \quad \sigma = \frac{P_0}{F_{comp}} \leq \sigma_{max}. \quad (14)$$

The shape factor and height of the element are determined as

$$k_{shape} = \frac{(D-d)}{4h}; \quad h = \frac{(1+k)f}{\varepsilon_{max}}, \quad (15)$$

and the modulus of compression and deformation from pretension are

$$E = \frac{(1+k)P_0}{\varepsilon_{max}F_{comp}}; \quad f = \frac{P_0h}{EF_{comp}}. \quad (16)$$

In accordance with the presented methods for calculating the dynamic lever-disk friction shock absorber of electric trains ER9E, a program was compiled for the Mathcad 15 programming environment by analogy with studies given in [4, 5, 6]. A mathematical model for the dynamic calculation of the details of a lever-disk friction shock absorber of electric trains is given in [7].

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